

Adaptive soft sensor to predict alite fraction clinker production through quasi-ensemble PLS modelling

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Alite is a form of tricalcium silicate that is the essential constituent of Portland cement clinkers. In cement industry, the alite fraction can be determined only through off-line laboratory measurements collected at a low frequency. However, due to digitalization, cement production plants are heavily instrumented and collect dozens, if not hundreds, of online measurements of process variables, e.g. kiln temperature, torque etc., at a high frequency, retaining the fingerprint of the product quality in terms of alite fraction (Lea et al., 2019). For this reason, soft sensors (Souza et al., 2016) can be utilized to exploit the wealth of information of the on-line collected data and estimate in real time the alite fraction. This study proposes an adaptive soft sensor capable of predicting the alite fraction of produced clinker from easy to measure process variables such as those mentioned above. The model is developed based on data taken from an industrial case study which is characterised by the following challenges: highly correlated variables, nonlinear and dynamic behaviour, typically due to seasonal effects or drifts for equipment aging and/or fouling. Thus, a latent-variable regression method, e.g. Partial Least Squares (PLS, (Geladi and Kowalski, 1986)), is used to estimate the alite fraction from online process measurements, while adaptive modelling (Joe Qin, 1998) is adopted to update the soft sensor to the changing features of the plant. Finally, local models are used to tailor the model adaptively on the characteristics of the most similar observations in the historical data to deal with nonlinearities. However, maximizing the accuracy of the soft sensor requires tuning several hyperparameters (e.g. the number of latent variables of the PLS models and the number of observations to build local models), whose optimal values identification is not trivial. Hence in this work we propose a technique inspired from ensemble modelling, but instead of using different training dataset partitions to construct the sub-models (Cao et al., 2017), we build the ensemble using different sets of values of the above-mentioned hyperparameters. Then, the estimations of the sub-models are averaged to obtain the final ensemble prediction of alite fraction, while variability identifies the estimation uncertainty. The very promising initial results are a strong indicator of this sensor's potential to becoming a core component in the next generation digital cement production plants.

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Cao, D., Deng, Z., Zhu, M., Yao, Z., Dong, J., Zhao, R., 2017. Ensemble partial least squares regression for descriptor selection, outlier detection, applicability domain assessment, and ensemble modeling in QSAR/QSPR modeling. *Journal of Chemometrics* 31, e2922. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cem.2922>

Geladi, P., Kowalski, B.R., 1986. Partial least-squares regression: a tutorial. *Analytica Chimica Acta* 185, 1–17. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-2670\(86\)80028-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-2670(86)80028-9)

Joe Qin, S., 1998. Recursive PLS algorithms for adaptive data modeling. *Computers & Chemical Engineering* 22, 503–514. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0098-1354\(97\)00262-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0098-1354(97)00262-7)

Lea, F.M., Hewlett, P.C., Liška, M. (Eds.), 2019. *Lea's chemistry of cement and concrete*, Fifth edition. ed. Butterworth-Heinemann, Oxford Cambridge.

Souza, F.A.A., Araújo, R., Mendes, J., 2016. Review of soft sensor methods for regression applications. *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems* 152, 69–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemolab.2015.12.011>